

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Digital Tools

Set of one-pagers

WP5– Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101093921

Adaptation AGORA digital tools

Premise: Under the capacity building activities, Adaptation AGORA has been developing different materials. They range from multimedia materials, like videos, recordings of webinars/conferences, to sets of slides, as well as content for the development of the two Academies. Adaptation AGORA is not responsible for the use of the materials (CC BY)

1. Link to the material: See annexes

2. Potential key entries to search material.

Category and Target: Category: Digital Tools; Target: University students, general public, NGOs, journalists, public authorities

3. Brief Introduction/Summary

Estimated time: 55 min

Objective: Overview of the Digital tools created by Adaptation AGORA

Type of resource: Set of slides

Language: English

4. Key Challenges/ issues addressed

Climate change disinformation, and which events and tools were developed by the project to combat this challenge.

5. What the Resource Offers

Overview of the Digital Tools created by Adaptation AGORA to tackle disinformation, production of educational material (interviews/videos), and capacity building for stakeholder engagement.

AGORA digitaalsete vahendite kohandamine

Adaptation AGORA on võimekuse suurendamise eesmärgil välja töötanud erinevaid materjale, nt nagu multimeediasisu (videod, veebiseminaride/konverentside salvestused), slaidikomplektide, samuti kahe akadeemia arendamiseks mõeldud sisu. Adaptation Agora ei vastuta materjalide kasutamise eest (CC BY).

1. Link materjalile

Vt lisad

2. Võimalikud märksõnad materjali otsimiseks.

Kategooria ja sihtrühm: Kategooria: Digitaalsed vahendid; Sihtrühm: Üliõpilased, üldsus, valitsusvälised organisatsioonid, ajakirjanikud, riigiasutused

3. Lühike sissejuhatus/kokkuvõte

Hinnanguline kestus: 55min

Eesmärk: Ülevaade Adaptation AGORA poolt loodud digitaalsetest tööriistadest

Ressursi tüüp: ppt

Keel: Inglise

4. Peamised väljakutsed/ lahendatavad probleemid

Kliimamuutustega seotud valeinfo ning üritused ja tööriistad, mis projekt selle väljakutse lahendamiseks välja töötas.

5. Mida ressurss pakub?

Ülevaade Adaptation AGORA poolt loodud digitaalsetest vahenditest valeinfo vastu võitlemiseks, õppematerjalide (intervjuud/videod) tootmiseks ja sidusrühmade kaasamise suutlikkuse suurendamiseks.

Adaptation AGORA outils numériques

Dans le cadre des activités de renforcement des capacités, Adaptation AGORA a développé différents supports. Ceux-ci incluent des contenus multimédias, tels que des vidéos, enregistrements de webinaires/conférences, des ensembles de diapositives, ainsi que des contenus pour le développement de deux Académies. L'utilisation de ces contenus, mis à disposition sous licence Creative Commons (CC BY), relève de la responsabilité des utilisateurs et non du projet Adaptation Agora (CC BY)

1. Lien vers le contenu: Voir annexes

2. Entrées clés potentielles pour rechercher du matériel.

Catégorie et cible : Catégorie : Outils numériques ; Cible : Étudiants universitaires, grand public, ONG, journalistes, autorités publiques

3. Brève introduction/résumé

Temps estimé : 35 min

Objectif : Présentation des outils numériques créés par Adaptation AGORA

Type de ressource : ppt

Langue : Anglais

4. Principaux défis/problèmes abordés

La désinformation sur le changement climatique et les événements ainsi que les outils développés par le projet pour relever ce défi.

5. Apports de la ressource

Aperçu des outils numériques créés par Adaptation AGORA pour lutter contre la désinformation, produire du matériel pédagogique (interviews/vidéos) et renforcer les capacités des parties prenantes.

Adaptation AGORA Digitale Werkzeuge

Im Rahmen der "Hilfe zur Selbsthilfe" - Aktivitäten hat das Projekt Adaptation AGORA verschiedene Materialien entwickelt. Diese beinhalten multimediale Inhalte wie Videos, Aufzeichnungen von Webinaren/Konferenzen, Foliensätze sowie Inhalte für die Entwicklung der beiden Online-Akademien. Adaptation AGORA ist nicht verantwortlich für die Nutzung der Ressourcen (CC BY).

1. Link zum Material: siehe Anhang

2. Potenzielle Suchbegriffe:

Kategorie und Zielgruppe: Kategorie: Digitale Tools; Zielgruppe: Studierende, allgemeine Öffentlichkeit, NGOs, Journalist*innen, Behörden

3. Kurze Einführung/Zusammenfassung

Geschätzte Zeit: 55min

Ziel: Übersicht über die von Adaptation AGORA entwickelten digitalen Werkzeuge

Ressourcentyp: Folien-Set

Sprache: Englisch

4. Zentrale Herausforderungen/Probleme, die adressiert werden

Desinformationen zum Klimawandel, sowie die Veranstaltungen und Instrumente, die im Rahmen des Projekts entwickelt wurden, um dieser Herausforderung zu begegnen.

5. Was die Ressource bietet

Übersicht über die von Adaptation AGORA entwickelten digitalen Werkzeuge zur Bekämpfung von Desinformation, zur Erstellung von Bildungsmaterialien (Interviews/Videos) und zum Kapazitätsaufbau für Stakeholder-Engagement.

Ψηφιακά εργαλεία του Adaptation AGORA

Σημείωση: Στο πλαίσιο των δραστηριοτήτων ανάπτυξης ικανοτήτων, το πρόγραμμα Adaptation AGORA έχει δημιουργήσει επιμορφωτικό και εκπαιδευτικό υλικό. Αυτό περιλαμβάνει πολυμεσικό υλικό, όπως βίντεο, μαγνητοσκοπημένα διαδικτυακά σεμινάρια/συνεδρία, παρουσιάσεις, καθώς και το περιεχόμενο που χρησιμοποιήθηκε για την ανάπτυξη των δύο διαδικτυακών Ακαδημιών. Το Adaptation Agora δεν φέρει ευθύνη για τη χρήση των υλικών (CC BY).

1. Σύνδεσμος προς το υλικό: βλέπε παραρτήματα

2. Πιθανοί βασικοί όροι αναζήτησης του υλικού.

Κατηγορία: Ψηφιακά εργαλεία

Ομάδες-στόχοι: Φοιτητές πανεπιστημίου, ευρύ κοινό, ΜΚΟ, δημοσιογράφοι, δημόσιες αρχές

3. Σύντομη εισαγωγή/περίληψη

Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος: 55 λεπτά

Σκοπός: Επισκόπηση των ψηφιακών εργαλείων που δημιουργήθηκαν από το Adaptation AGORA

Τύπος υλικού: Σειρά διαφανειών

Γλώσσα: Αγγλικά

4. Βασικές προκλήσεις/ζητήματα που αντιμετωπίζονται

Παραπληροφόρηση σχετικά με την κλιματική αλλαγή, οι δράσεις που πραγματοποιήθηκαν ποια γεγονότα και εργαλεία αναπτύχθηκαν από το έργο για την αντιμετώπιση αυτής της πρόκλησης.

5. Τι προσφέρει το υλικό

Επισκόπηση των ψηφιακών εργαλείων που ανέπτυξε το Adaptation AGORA για την αντιμετώπιση της παραπληροφόρησης, την παραγωγή εκπαιδευτικού υλικού (όπως συνεντεύξεις και βίντεο) και την ενίσχυση των δεξιοτήτων για τη συμμετοχή των ενδιαφερομένων.

Progetto Adaptation AGORA, strumenti digitali

Nell'ambito delle attività di capacity building, Adaptation AGORA ha sviluppato diversi materiali che spaziano da contenuti multimediali, come video e registrazioni di webinar/conferenze, presentazioni in power point, nonché contenuti per lo sviluppo delle due Accademie.

Adaptation Agora non è responsabile dell'utilizzo dei materiali (CC BY)

1. Link Alla risorsa: vedi allegati

2. Parole chiave per cercare la risorsa

Categoria: strumenti digitali

Destinatari: pubblico generale, studenti universitari, NGO, giornalisti, autorità pubbliche

3. Sintesi

Tempo stimato per la consultazione della risorsa: 55min

Obiettivo: presentazione generale sugli strumenti digitali sviluppati all'interno del progetto

Tipo di risorsa: presentazione power point

Lingua: Inglese

4. Principali sfide/problematiche affrontate

Disinformazione climatica, e quali eventi e strumenti sono stati organizzati e sviluppati dal progetto per contrastare questa problematica

5. Cosa offre la risorsa

Overview generale sugli strumenti digitali creati dal progetto Adaptation AGORA per combattere la disinformazione, la produzione di materiali educativi tipo video interviste ed eventi di capacity building per il coinvolgimento degli stakeholder.

Herramientas digitales de Adaptation AGORA

En el marco de las actividades de desarrollo de capacidades, Adaptation AGORA ha elaborado diversos materiales. Estos abarcan desde materiales multimedia, como vídeos y grabaciones de seminarios web y conferencias, hasta conjuntos de diapositivas, así como contenidos para el desarrollo de las dos academias. Adaptation Agora no se hace responsable del uso de los materiales (CC BY).

1. Enlace al material: Ver anexos

2. Posibles entradas clave para buscar el material

Categoría: Herramientas digitales

Target: Estudiantes universitarios, público en general, ONG, periodistas, autoridades públicas

3. Breve introducción/resumen

Tiempo estimado: 55min

Objetivo: Descripción general de las herramientas digitales creadas por Adaptation AGORA

Tipo de recurso: Conjunto de diapositivas

Idioma: Inglés

4. Retos clave/temas abordados

Desinformación sobre el cambio climático y qué ha desarrollado el proyecto y qué eventos se han organizado para combatir este reto

5. Qué ofrece el recurso

Descripción general de las herramientas digitales creadas por Adaptation AGORA para combatir la desinformación, la producción de material educativo (entrevistas/vídeos) y el desarrollo de capacidades para la participación de las partes interesadas.

Adaptation AGORA: Digitala verktyg

Adaptation AGORA har tagit fram olika material för kapacitetsutveckling. Dessa inkluderar allt från multimediamaterial, såsom videor och inspelningar av webbseminarier och konferenser, till bildsamlingar och material för utvecklingen av de två akademierna.

Adaptation AGORA ansvarar inte för hur materialen används (CC BY).

1. Länk till materialet: Se bilagor

2. Potentiella nyckelposter för att söka material.

Kategori och mål: Kategori: Digitala verktyg; Målgrupp: Universitetsstuderande, allmänheten, icke-statliga organisationer, journalister, och myndigheter

3. Kort introduktion/sammanfattning

Beräknad tid: 55min

Mål: Översikt över digitala verktyg skapade inom Adaptation AGORA

Typ av resurs: Bildsamling

Språk: Engelska

4. Viktiga utmaningar/frågor som tas upp

Klimatdesinformation, samt de evenemang och verktyg som har tagits fram av projekt för att bekämpa denna utmaning.

5. Vad resursen erbjuder

Översikt över de digitala verktyg som skapats inom Adaptation AGORA för att bekämpa desinformation, utbildningsmaterial (intervjuer/videor), och kapacitetsutveckling för samarbete och samverkan.

Annex: Resource

adaptation Agora in a nutshell

Adaptation AGORA is a HORIZON Europe 3-years project started in January 2023 and coordinated by the CMCC Foundation.

Aligning with the overall goals of the EU Mission on Climate Change Adaptation, AGORA project:

- promotes **social transformation processes** in diverse contexts through transdisciplinary tools and approaches;
- encourages **effective engagement of citizens and communities in actions against climate change**;
- accelerates the local adaptation processes to build a Europe resilient to climate change.

Digital Academies in Adaptation AGORA

Digital Academy to access and use Climate Data and monitor Climate Risks

This Digital Academy aims to:

- Identify, provide access to, and share guidance on how to use various open source climate and risk data
- Provide easy access to information
- Empower citizens, stakeholders, and policy makers
- Enhance the visualisation of climate information

Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation

This Digital Academy aims to provide access to:

- Trustworthy information
- Fact-checked reports and documents
- Relevant and emerging resources
- Bi-annual reports

Why information is important for engagement

Information as the basis for an active participation of citizens in the democratic process and climate action.

Information is key for an effective engagement

Exploring the Digital Academy

<https://agoraclimatedisinfo.eu/>

The Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation

The Academy aims to enhance public and stakeholder skills to combat **climate change disinformation**, equipping them with reliable **climate change information** and **fact-checked data** from **credible sources**. It offers comprehensive resources and educational materials empowering users to **tackle the main fake news** about climate change and **promoting media literacy**.

Exploring the Digital Academy: Climate Disinformation

- Five training modules about **climate change, climate change communication and climate disinformation tactics**;
- Deepening on the **climate disinformation most common narratives** with a **"submit your fact-check"** section that allows users to contribute actively to the fight against climate change disinformation;
- **Bi-annual reports**.

Exploring the Digital Academy: Media Literacy

- Seven training modules to promote media literacy: **fact-checking and verification, critical thinking and fallacies, evaluation of the sources** (...)

Exploring the Digital Academy: Resources

A series of **fact checks, reports and papers** helping users to **separate facts from myths and stop the spread of disinformation**.

Disinformation narratives debunking methodology

Stephan Lewandowsky, John Cook, Doug Lombardi, *"Debunking Handbook 2020"* *

FACT	Lead with the fact if it's clear, pithy, and sticky—make it simple, concrete, and plausible. It must "fit" with the story.
WARN ABOUT THE MYTH	Warn beforehand that a myth is coming... mention it once only.
EXPLAIN FALLACY	Explain how the myth misleads.
FACT	Finish by reinforcing the fact—multiple times if possible. Make sure it provides an alternative causal explanation.

* *Debunking Handbook 2020*: www.climatechangecommunication.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/DebunkingHandbook2020.pdf

Tools to tackle disinformation: the MOBILE APP

The gamified mobile app aims to support the **education of citizens** on climate change adaptation and **counter disinformation campaigns** through an **entertaining and engaging approach**.

By incorporating **interactive elements**, such as a scoreboard or ranking, the app will transform learning into an interactive and fun experience, **encouraging engagement and active participation from stakeholders**.

Communication and dissemination

Session at EGU 2024

Telling climate stories: platforms, tools, and methodologies for accurate and engaging science communication.

WP5_Capacity building for stakeholder engagement_events

Climate news and fake news. Navigating the climate crisis between science and information.

Roundtable organised in collaboration with WWF Italy to raise awareness on the topic of climate disinformation.

The event offered an analysis of the state of the art and a series of tools that allowed the audience to distinguish fake news from correct information, based on scientific grounds.

Audience: media, institutions, academia, NGOs, citizens.

Reach: 267 attendees online + about 25 in the conference room.

WP5_Capacity building for stakeholder engagement_events

Event on disinformation in Spain

Online event
10 April 2024
Disinformation in schools

Verificat is a non-profit organization with a mission for social impact. It is a fact-checking and education platform for responsible consumption and production of information.

Breakout rooms and gaming approach.

Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

Teach people the FLICK framework through gaming: Range of ways how misinformation can mislead people they can learn and recognize those techniques

They become resilient to misinformation: vaccine/inoculation theory

The holy grail of fact-checking: Automatically detecting and debunking misinformation in realtime

- Study to train a machine learning model to identify and debunk misinformation and test it on 5.000 tweets of misinformation bits
- Study to apply the logic-based approach to train the model to detect the different fallacies you find in climate disinformation – you enter some text in an interactive interface and it tells you what's the fallacy behind according to the FLICK taxonomy.

Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

Production of educational contents:

Video interviews

Educational videos

